

Polarographic Studies on Acidic Aminoacid Imines (N-Salicylidene-1-aspartic Acid and N-Salicylidene-1-glutamic Acid)

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Polarographic studies of N-salicylidene-1-aspartic acid and N-salicylidene-1-glutamic acid have been made at the DME at different pH, temperatures, concentrations and in the presence of some surfactants in aqueous B. R. buffers, at constant ionic strength. Single well-defined cathodic irreversible waves were observed for which two-electron reduction mechanism with radical anion formation has been proposed.

ASPARTIC and glutamic acids being acidic amino acids, play a major role in biological processes like transamination¹, decarboxylation², cell metabolism³ and neurotransmission⁴ reactions. The biological importance of amino acid imines was recognized by Metzler, Ikawa and Snell⁵.

Zuman⁶ has given an indirect polarographic method for the estimation of amino acids by converting them into suitable imines which are easily reducible at the dropping mercury electrode (dme).

The polarographic reduction of various, substituted imines has been investigated earlier⁷⁻⁹. In the present communication, we report polarographic reduction studies of N-salicylidene-1-aspartic acid (NSA) and N-salicylidene-1-glutamic acid (NSG) at the dme. The influence of pH, temperature, concentration, mercury pressure and surfactants has been studied which has thrown light on their mode of reduction.

Experimental

NSA and NSG were prepared by the method given by Smith¹⁰ in which piperidine, was used as a base catalyst. The synthesis was confirmed by spot reactions and ninhydrin test; the purity of compound was checked by tlc wherein only one spot was observed. In spectral studies the uv peaks were observed at 287 and 289 nm for NSA and NSG respectively which are characteristic of >C=N-linkage¹¹. The ir absorption peaks were similarly observed at 1600 and 1630 cm⁻¹ for NSA and NSG respectively. The imines were also characterized by elemental analysis for molecular formula C₁₁H₁₂O₅N for NSA, m.p. 478°K and for molecular formula C₁₂H₁₄O₅N for NSG, m.p. 497°K.

Polarograms were recorded with a Toshniwal manual polarograph No. 039 using a saturated

calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode. The capillary of the dropping mercury electrode had the following characteristics:

$m = 1.55 \text{ mg S}^{-1}$; $t = 3.53 \text{ S}$ at $E = -1.10 \text{ V vs SCE}$ in closed circuit and $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 1.652 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ S}^{-1/6}$.

Deaeration was carried out by passing pure oxygen-free nitrogen in the polarographic cell for about 20 min before the study and subsequently an atmosphere of nitrogen was maintained over the test solution. Aqueous solutions of imines were prepared in freshly double distilled water.

Results and Discussion

Influence of pH: NSA and NSG gave single well defined waves at all the pH values ranging from 2.1 to 11.0. NSA gave a sharp maximum at pH 2.10 which was suppressed by the addition of 0.002% Triton X-100. The slope values of the log plot analysis for both the imines are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - CHARACTERISTICS OF POLAROGRAPHIC WAVES OF N-SALICYLIDENE-1-ASPARTIC ACID (NSA) and N-SALICYLIDENE-1-GLUTAMIC ACID (NSG)

pH	B. R. buffer medium Ionic Strength I = 0.5		Conc. = $2.56 \times 10^{-3} M$ Temp. = $303^{\circ} \pm 0.1^{\circ} K$	Slope values of log plots in V
	$-E_{1/2}$ volts vs S.C.E.	i_d in μA		
N-Salicylidene-1-aspartic acid (NSA)				
2.10	1.045	1.460	0.058, 0.044	
4.20	1.185	2.133	0.050	
7.17	1.330	1.200	0.072	
9.17	1.470	4.133	0.062	
11.02	1.770	6.800	0.074	
N-Salicylidene-1-glutamic acid (NSG)				
2.10	1.030	0.933	0.090	
4.20	1.190	2.133	0.054	
7.17	1.320	1.500	0.066, 0.052	
9.17	1.482	7.200	0.068, 0.042	
11.02	1.820	4.400	0.044, 0.036	

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Typical polarograms of $2.56 \times 10^{-3} M$ concentrations are recorded in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1. Polarographic curves of N-salicylidene-1-aspartic acid in aqueous B. R. buffer at 0.5 ionic strength: A pH 2.10; B 4.20; C 7.17; D 9.17; E=11.02; Conc. 2.56 mM.

Fig. 2. Polarographic curves of N-salicylidene-1-glutamic acid in aqueous B. R. buffer at 0.5 ionic strength: A pH 2.10; B 4.20; C 7.17; D 9.17; E 11.02; Conc. 2.56 mM.

Influence of concentration: Studies were made at depolarizer concentration of 2.56 to 9.52 mM in B.R. buffer from pH 2.10 to 11.02 at $I=0.5$. The i_l/C values varied with concentration in a peculiar manner. The results are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—RELATION BETWEEN LIMITING CURRENT AND DEPOLARIZER CONCENTRATION

Conc. mM	i_l/C at different pH values					
	pH	2.1	4.2	7.2	9.2	11.0
N-Salicylidene-1-aspartic acid (NSA)						
2.56		0.607	0.834	0.478	1.714	1.023
5.00		0.384	0.532	0.352	1.649	1.361
7.31		0.307	0.479	0.312	1.621	1.417
9.52		0.284	0.375	0.201	1.605	1.197
N-Salicylidene-1-glutamic acid (NSG)						
2.56		0.405	0.829	0.603	3.161	1.004
5.00		0.254	0.458	0.926	2.846	0.625
7.31		0.353	0.331	0.792	2.637	0.803
9.52		0.425	0.630	0.850	2.530	0.902

Influence of mercury pressure: The experiments were made in the range of 20 to 60 cm height of mercury column at selected pH range in B.R. buffer at $303^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ K$. The $i_l/h^{3/2}$ corr. values decreased with increasing height in each case.

Influence of temperature: The influence of varying the temperature was studied at pH 4.0, $I=0.5$ between $303^\circ K$ and with intervals of 5° . The values of temperature coefficient varied from 2.69 to 3.02 for NSG and 2.54 to 3.10 for NSA.

Influence of surfactants: Camphor or thymol was added to the test solution. On increasing the concentration of camphor or thymol, the wave heights decreased gradually and the $E_{1/2}$ of the waves shifted towards negative potentials.

These imines are biprotic, tridentate ligands which contain a phenolic hydroxy group, two carboxylic groups, phenyl ring and an imine linkage $>C=N-$. The $-OH$ group is located at the *ortho* position to the imine linkage which leads to an increase in the charge density on $>C=N-$ or imine linkage. The possible reduction site in the molecule is the azomethine linkage where the presence of a lone-electron pair on nitrogen makes the molecule susceptible to reduction.

At low pH values the presence of $-COOH$ groups facilitate the reduction of imine linkage at less negative potentials whereas at higher pH, a shift in $E_{1/2}$ to more negative potential is observed due to the formation of $-(COO^-)$ carboxylate ion and the presence of $-OH$ group. The negative shift of $E_{1/2}$ values with increasing pH indicates the involvement of protons¹². The $-OH$ groups does not partake in electroreduction as it forms intramolecular hydrogen bonding with imine linkage with resulting mesomeric effect¹³ in the molecule.

The high log-plot slope values indicate irreversible nature¹⁴ of the electrode process. Further, the limiting current values do not appear to increase in proportion to the concentration. The values of $i_l/h^{3/2}$ corr., also decrease with increasing mercury pressure. All these observations indicate that the reduction is kinetically controlled¹⁵ at least partially. The plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs pH values in each case, do

not yield a straight line but the points lie on two straight lines. The average variation of $E_{1/2}$ for NSA per pH unit was found to be 0.06 volt in acidic pH range and 0.09 volt per pH unit in alkaline media, whereas the average variation of $E_{1/2}$ for NSG per pH unit is 0.06 volt in acidic pH and 0.08 volt in alkaline pH. These facts indicate that proton is involved in each step of reduction.

On the basis of the foregoing facts, the mechanism of reduction of both the imines can be represented as follows :

where Ar=carbonyl residue and A=coupled amino acid residue.

The first step is slow and rate determining.

Such electron transfer processes have been evaluated earlier also¹⁶ and similar mechanism has been proposed by Scott and Jura¹⁷ for the reduction of aromatic Schiff's bases.

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